

Knowledge Management for Autonomous Systems and Computational Intelligence

J.UCS Special Issue

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This special issue of the Journal of Universal Computer Science contains selected and extended papers presented at the *Second International Symposium on Agent and Multi-agent Systems: Technology and Applications (KES-AMSTA 2008)*, which was successfully held in Incheon, Korea, March 26 – 28, 2008. This symposium is the successful second event in the international symposium series on Agent and Multi-agent Systems, chaired by N.T. Nguyen and supported by KES International. The second group of papers consists of those selected and extended from the *2008 International Conference on Intelligent Computing*, held on September 15–18, 2008 in Shanghai, China, chaired by D.S. Huang. For both conferences the proceedings were published by Springer in the prestigious series LNAI. Each paper included in this issue contains at least 40% new material in comparison with the conference paper. All invited papers have been reviewed by three well known specialists in the fields in double-blind mode and only those with the highest scores have been accepted.

We cordially thank the reviewers for their valuable reviews which guarantee the high quality of the accepted papers. Special thanks go to the authors for their contributions to this special issue. Finally, we would like to thank Professor Hermann Maurer, the Managing Editor of J.UCS, and Dana Kaiser for their support in editing this issue.

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